

Supplementary Tukey Table. Comparison of the averages for variables Q1 and Q4 that interacted between variation sources (gender vs. age and sex vs. income).

AGE						
		AGED 4-9	AGED 10-14	AGED 15-20		
Q1	M	3.28Aa	4.19Ba	4.03Bb		
	F	3.24Aa	4.59Ba	2.85Aa		
Q4	M	1.41Aa	2.00Bb	2.39Bb		
	F	1.54Aa	1.55Aa	1.81Aa		
INCOME						
		<2 SM	2-3 SM	3-5 SM	4-10 SM	>10 SM
Q4	M	2.16Bb	2.15Bb	1.91Bb	1.62ABa	1.11Aa
	F	1.80Aa	1.35Aa	1.43Aa	1.12Aa	1.00Aa

Means followed by different lowercase letters in the column (gender) and uppercase letters in the row (age or income) differ from each other by the Tukey test at 5%